

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D1.4 Testing and validation methodology

Document Summary Information

Start Date	01/01/2021	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.vital5g.eu		
Deliverable	D1.4 Testing and Validation methodology		
Related Work Package	WP1	Related Task	Task 1.4
Contractual due date	31/12/2021	Actual submission date	20/12/2021
Type	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Editor	Andreas Kartakoullis (eBOS), George Guirgis (eBOS)		

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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.0	01/09/2021	0	Initial Deliverable Structure	George Guirgis (eBOS)
V0.1a	15/10/2021	3%	Input to Section 1	Andreas Kartakoullis (eBOS)
V0.1b	11/11/2021	4%	Table of Content Restructuring	Andreas Kartakoullis (eBOS), George Guirgis (eBOS), Ronan Frizzell (INLE), Kostas Trichias (WINGS)
V0.2	18/11/2021	35%	Input to Section 4 and Section 5	Ronan Frizzell (INLE)
V0.3	19/11/2021	55%	Input to Section 2 and Section 3	Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), George Guirgis (EBOS)
V0.4	22/11/2021	70%	Input to Section 3	Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Ilias Kotinas (WINGS), Aristotelis Margaris (INCE), Kostas Tsagkaris (INCE)
V0.5	23/11/2021	80%	Input to Section 5	Esteban Municio (IMEC), Nina Slamnik-Krijestorac (IMEC), Christina Lessi (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO)
V0.6	24/11/2021	85%	Additional contributions to Section 4 and Section 5	Ronan Frizzell (INLE)
V0.7	25/11/2021	90%	Contributions to all Sections	Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Giada Landi (NXW)
V0.8	03/12/2021	95%	Refinement of text and formatting and ready for peer-review	Andreas Kartakoullis (eBOS), George Guirgis (eBOS)
V0.9	15/12/2021	99%	Incorporated peer review feedback and version reviewed by quality control	Giada Landi (NXW), Javier Rivas (DHL), Andreas Kartakoullis (eBOS)
V1.0	16/12/2021	100%	Final quality control and coordinator review	Kostas Trichias (WINGS)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-PPP	5G Public-Private Partnership
5G SA	5G Standalone Access
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AMF	Access & Mobility Management Function
API	Application Programming Interface
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
BBU	Baseband Unit
CaaS	Connectivity as a Service
CNF	Cloud-native Network Functions
CSV	Comma Separated Value
D-ITG	Distributed Internet Traffic Generator
DL	Downlink
DNN	Data Network Name
E2E	End-to-End
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
FDD	Frequency Division Duplex
gNBs	gNodeBs
GUI	Graphic User Interface
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LS	Lean Startup
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
mMIMO	massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MNO	Mobile Network Operators
MOS	Mean Opinion Score

MVP	Minimum Viable Product
N/A	Not Applicable
NBI	North Bound Interface
NRF	Network Function Repository Function
NS	Network Slice
OBU	Onboard Unit
PD	Performance Diagnosis
POTP	Packet Optical Transport
QoE	Quality of Experience
QPSK	Quadrature Phase Shift Keying
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RSTP	Rapid Spanning Tree Protocol
RTT	Round Trip Time
SA	System Architecture
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SNSSAI	Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SST	Slice Service Type
SUT	System Under Test
T&L	Transport & Logistics
TF	Traffic Flow
TaaS	Testing as a Service
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UC	Use Case
UDP	Universal Datagram Protocol
UDM	Unified Data Management
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra High Definition
UL	Uplink
UPF	User Plane Function

URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VS	Vertical Specific
VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
WebRTC	Web Real-Time Communication

Executive Summary

The testing and validation methodology to be elaborated in this deliverable is two-fold. The first fold is about the technology validation that entails the steps, procedures and framework to be used to test and evaluate the functionalities and the performances of 5G-enabled and NetApp-based T&L services and 5G network communications over the VITAL-5G platform. The second fold centres around the business validation methodology to fully exploit the business potential of VITAL-5G platform by engaging third-party experimenters such as start-ups and enterprises. More specifically, the deliverable describes an initial engagement plan designed for attracting the third-party experimenters. The work is accomplished as the main output of Task 'T1.4 - Testing & Validation methodology' and performed under work package 'WP1 - Use Cases, Requirements Analysis and Architecture'.

In particular, as far as the **technology validation** is concerned, **a customized Testcase template is presented and procedures for completing it are defined**, by giving a comprehensive description for all the important aspects and KPIs of the planned experiments. Furthermore, an explanation is given on how these KPIs will be used and analyzed by the VITAL-5G platform to produce and present the KPI values in a user-friendly form.

For **the business validation** we will use the **lean startup methodology** that centers around the main **motivations of a business**. The inputs will include, apart from the business case itself, end-user feedback from their direct engagement in the trials of the T&L use cases. The corresponding **outputs will be validations that will allow to identify those use cases and the corresponding NetApps that have the highest commercialization potential** so as to progress to the next step of creating a service product portfolio. For this purpose, we will **use a set of questionnaires, surveys and focused group workshops directly engaging other T&L actors**.

1 Introduction

VITAL-5G focuses on the design and implementation of a flexible 5G experimentation facility that can host network applications which will optimize the performance and the efficiency of services in the Transport & Logistics (T&L) sector. For that purpose, a variety of 5G-enabled NetApps from the VITAL-5G consortium partners, as well as third party experimenters, will be developed to address specific T&L industry challenges. The experimentation services offered by the VITAL-5G facility will allow the third parties to early test and experimentally validate the new features and enhanced performances enabled by the adoption of the 5G technology in their applications and services. In order to showcase the advantages of VITAL-5G solution, three Use Cases (UC) are designed in three VITAL-5G testbeds:

- UC1: Automated vessel transport, which will be tested in the port of Antwerp,
- UC2: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras, which will be tested in the Galati port,
- UC3: Automation and remote operation of freight logistics, which will be tested in Athens logistics hub.

These three initial UCs, which have been documented in D1.1 [1] will be complemented with additional NetApps, T&L vertical services and, potentially, new UCs to be proposed and developed by third parties.

This document provides a description of the technology testing methodology for executing, documenting and validating the VITAL-5G platform experiments, of the business validation methodology including a feedback questionnaire from third-party experimenters, and a preliminary third-party experimenters engagement plan. Additionally, Testcase templates filled for two specific testing scenarios are given as an example for the completion of all the necessary validation tests during the project.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T1.4 Testing & Validation methodology	The testing and validation methodology to be elaborated in this task entails the acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technology and business validation of the T&L NetApps and associated use cases.	Chapter 2 Chapter 3 Chapter 4	Chapter 2 is describing the evaluation principles and methodology. Chapter 3 is describing the testing and technical validation methodology and the Testcase documentation defined through T1.4. Chapter 4 is describing the business validation procedure.
T1.4 Testing & Validation methodology	The basic concept behind evaluation methodology that will be used in this task.	Chapter 2	Evaluation methodology principles are described in Chapter 2.

T1.4 Testing & Validation methodology	The technology validation procedure will be defined in this task. A detailed description of the testing and validation methodology is given, followed by a thorough presentation of a Testcase template to collect the data feeds from the 5G nodes and other relevant equipment, stating also how these feeds will be used and analyzed by the VITAL-5G users to produce and present the KPI values in a user-friendly form.	Chapter 3	In Chapter 3 a comprehensive description of the technological validation methodology is given, with a testcase template and concrete examples to fill it.
T1.4 Testing & Validation methodology	For the business validation we will use the lean startup methodology that will use user feedback from their direct engagement in the trials of the T&L use cases.	Chapter 4	Lean startup methodology will be used to assess the commercialization potential of the use cases.
T1.4 Testing & Validation methodology	A preliminary engagement plan for third-party experimenters is presented. Additionally, third party engagement KPIs are defined.	Chapter 5	Chapter 5 is presenting the first version of the engagement plan for third-party experimenters.
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D1.4 Report on testing and validation methodology</p> <p>Report containing the principles on technology and business validation that will be applied in the VITAL-5G project, including the Testcase template and an initial plan on third party engagement.</p>			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The overall structure of this deliverable can be summarized as follows:

Section 1: Introduction and brief description of the deliverable.

Section 2: Describes the overall evaluation methodology for both business and technological evaluation and the inputs from other tasks to complete the whole methodology.

Section 3: Describes the steps, procedures and framework to be used to enable the testing and validation of NetApp-based T&L services over the VITAL-5G platform. A detailed description of the developed Testcase template is given with two dummy Testcase reports as an example on how it should be completed.

Section 4: Provides the business validation methodology and approach, including questionnaires for feedback evaluation from the different type of VITAL-5G users.

Section 5: Provides an initial plan on how to engage third-party experimenters, including engagement activities and third-party engagement KPIs.

2 General Evaluation Methodology

This section will describe the overall VITAL-5G evaluation methodology, in addition to its interdependencies with relevant tasks from other work packages. The task at hand ‘T1.4 Testing & Validation methodology’ will detail (Section 3 and 4) on the test procedures, templates and benchmarks definition to evaluate from a technical and a business perspective NetApps, T&L services and use cases developed by project partners or third parties.

2.1 Workflow and Interdependencies

In order to reach the targeted granular level of testing and validation, a high arching method had to be established among the various components in order to ensure homogeneity throughout. This was accomplished through regular work package level meetings with open discussions among the partners responsible for design and/or development of the various components.

Input to T1.4 (see Figure 1) included the following:

- WP1 Use Cases, Requirements Analysis and Architecture
 - Task 1.1 Use case requirements and analysis
 - UC analysis, requirements and corresponding platform functionalities
 - Task 1.2 VITAL-5G Platform functional requirements analysis & specifications
 - 5G testbeds and platform requirements
 - NetApps specifications and interfaces
 - Task 1.3 VITAL-5G platform and 5G-testbed Architecture design
 - VITAL-5G Platform analysis and specifications
- WP5 Commercialization & Innovation
 - T5.1 Market analysis
 - Specify Market needs
 - Identify target audience and sectors

Figure 1: Flowchart presenting the interdependencies of the current deliverable

2.2 General Testing & Validation Phases Aspects

After the various input detailed above, the validation phases followed a *business-to-technology-to-business* method, that will go beyond the boundaries of this current task to provide the overall validation for innovation and business prospective.

Considering now the overall Testing and Validation methodology for the innovation development of VITAL-5G, we need to define three validation steps as Figure 2 illustrates. The first step is to define the problems and needs through market analysis (under T5.1) and thus identifying the business value that will be achieved from solving these defined problems. Then the problem statements are mapped to requirements under each UC (T1.1), which is then used to design the platform and its specifications (T1.2, T1.3), in addition to producing the testing procedures and specifications for each UC, following the template defined in chapter 3. This phase will also utilize the procedures and templates during the actual testing of the solutions, performed within the various tasks under ‘WP4 Testing & Validation Vertical Trials’. Finally, after the platform is finalized, its success and value will be proven through (UC) end-user workshops, and engagement, whereby proving that benefits from the VITAL-5G solution exist, as well as market opportunities. This will be detailed in chapter 4 and performed under ‘Task 5.2 Commercialization strategy and business plan’.

Figure 2: The entire validation procedure of D1.4 Testing and Validation Methodology

3 Technology Validation

VITAL-5G platform is a complete system that comprises hardware, software, and 5G connectivity components and it will be implemented in three different 5G PPP testbeds already established from the H2020-ICT-17-2018 5G-EVE project (Athens and Galati) [2] and the H2020-ICT-53 5G-Blueprint project (Antwerp) [3], properly extended and updated. The main objective of this section is the technology validation of this system by providing at Section 3.2 a comprehensive Testcase Template for System Under Test (SUT) experiments that can be used for the proposed T&L services and 5G network performance testing at the three different testbeds.

3.1 High-level Testing and Validation Procedures

The testing & validation methodology to be followed in VITAL-5G will define the steps, procedures and framework to be used to enable the testing and validation of NetApp-based T&L services over the VITAL-5G platform. In essence VITAL-5G plans to offer Testing as a Service (TaaS) to allow for the automated execution and evaluation of network-oriented and/or service-oriented testcases, based on high-level test plan descriptions of the intended experiments, and based on the experimentation service principals and available platform tools as defined in VITAL-5G deliverables D1.2 [4] and D2.1 [5]. The VITAL-5G testing & validation framework will offer advanced testing capabilities, utilizing the testbed-specific monitoring and testing tools as well as the globally available platform testing and validation tools, to enable the validation of network and vertical services across all three VITAL-5G trial sites. Access to these capabilities will be provided to the experimenters in a central manner via the VITAL-5G portal, through which they will be able to define their experiment, configure the specific testcases of interest, define the validation parameters and receive the validation report. The following sub-sections discuss in more detail the processes and tools of the VITAL-5G testing & validation framework.

3.1.1 Testing & Validation procedure

The testing & validation procedure is an integral part of the VITAL-5G experimentation service as described in Section 3 of D1.2 [4]. After the definition of the vertical service, using the tools and templates provided by the VITAL-5G platform and portal, the testing and validation parameters are configured and the experiment execution phase begins. Constant experiment monitoring will be available by the VITAL-5G platform, while after the experiment(s) have conducted, a detailed performance evaluation and service assessment phase is enabled. The exact stages of the VITAL-5G experimentation service are described in detail in Section 3.3 of D1.2 [4], and provide the end-to-end view of the experimentation procedure. The testing and validation procedure is the part of this end-to-end experimentation service, which focuses on the detailed definition of the tests to be executed, their successful execution and monitoring of the experiments, the metrics collection and storage and the post-processing and evaluation of the metrics, in order to validate the service under test, according to the validation KPIs provided by the experimenter.

The Testing and Validation procedure to be followed in VITAL-5G and its discrete stages, are depicted in Figure 3. The various stages of this procedure are explained below, while the overall VITAL-5G Testing & Validation framework and the definition of all its components are presented in Section 3.1.2.

Figure 3: VITAL-5G Testing & Validation procedure

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101016567

- **Stage 1 – Experiment Design**: This stage is inherited from the VITAL-5G experimentation service steps and it includes the detailed definition of the experiments to be executed, in validation of a specific T&L service or in validation of network performance under specific conditions. Besides the definition and configuration of the various NetApps and services, what is of particular importance here is the detailed completion of the VITAL-5G **Testcase template**, which will provide the necessary context and information for the specific test(s). The testcase is one of the most powerful tools of the VITAL-5G testing & validation framework and it defines for each experiment important testing & validation parameters, such as the selected testbed, 5G networks configuration (including slicing parameters), the metrics to be logged during the experiment execution, the evaluation formulas, the validation conditions and thresholds and more. A detailed description of the VITAL-5G Testcase template is provided in Section 3.2.
- **Stage 2 – Experiment Execution**: During the experiment execution stage, the various local (testbed) and global (platform) monitoring and metric/data collection tools are engaged and are continuously collecting information according to the measurement points, requirements and KPIs defined in the testcase by the experimenter. Real-time visualization of the experimentation status is supported during this stage, via the VITAL-5G portal and its monitoring/visualization tools, as described in deliverables D1.2 [4] and D2.1 [5]. The Service Testing & Experiment Manager and Service & Network Monitoring modules (see D1.2 [4]) are active during this stage, the former to coordinate the execution of the test scripts in case of automated testing and the latter to collect and visualize all the collected monitoring data.
- **Stage 3 – Results Evaluation & Service Validation**: In this stage the performance of the network and/or service components are evaluated, and the service functions are validated according to the target KPIs and the calculation and validation criteria provided by the experimenter (via the testcase). This stage engages the Results Analytics (RA) module and the Performance Diagnosis module (see Sections 5.5 and 5.6 of D2.1 [5], respectively), to perform the analysis of the collected results and to provide insights regarding the performance of the various selected components, as well as of the end-to-end service (if applicable).
- **Stage 4 – Experiment Finalization**: This stage is responsible for the proper wrap-up of the experimentation activities and the results visualization and reporting. Through the latter, the necessary feedback to the experimenter is provided, regarding the results analysis and validation, performed in the previous stage. The feedback to the experimenter is provided via the visualization tools of the VITAL-5G portal and the respective dashboards, while an experiment report will also be made available, after the conclusion of the experimentation. This stage also includes the proper storage (locally or on the cloud) and annotation of the collected metrics so they can be later accessed and/or downloaded by the experimenter for further processing.

3.1.2 VITAL-5G Testing & Validation Framework

The above-described process shows the step-by-step approach provided by the VITAL-5G platform and portal to allow for the testing and validation of various network configurations and T&L services. This process is coordinated by the **Testing & Validation framework** developed by VITAL-5G, which governs the interconnection and interfacing of the various testbed and platform modules, to enable necessary NetApp and Service onboarding and configuration, the definition of specific tests in great detail, the

data/metric collections and their processing and storage. The VITAL-5G Testing & Validation framework is depicted in Figure 4, and shows the functional components of the testbeds and the platform that are engaged in the testing and validation process. Each of the components of the framework and their exact functionality, are described in detail in deliverable D1.2 [4] and their software modules are specified in D2.1 [5]. For the sake of completeness, a brief description of each element is provided here as well (see Table 2), focusing on the element’s role in the testing and validation process, while a link to the detailed description of the element in the other VITAL-5G deliverables, will also be provided.

Figure 4: VITAL-5G Testing & Validation Framework

Table 2: VITAL-5G Testing & Validation elements role

Testing & Validation Element	Role in T&V process	Detailed element definition
Service Blueprint (incl. NetApp blueprint)	The Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) includes the list of the service components, which in VITAL-5G are NetApps, with details about their endpoints and interconnectivity. The VSB provides additional information related to the service logic, such as application or infrastructure-level monitoring metrics and a number of customizable service parameters (e.g., service level, 5G connectivity requirements, monitoring info).	Section 2.2.1 of D2.1 Section 2.2.2 of D2.1 [5]

	The NetApp blueprint provides the vertical service level information required to enable the construction of the T&L service chains which include vertical service block structure, mapping to interfaces and protocols, slice profile, etc.	
Testcase	The Testcase provides all the necessary experiment settings, to perform network or service-oriented experiments and to make them reproducible, including testbed selection, network/slice configuration, test environment, conditions and route, validation KPIs, measurement methodology and more.	Section 3.2 of D1.4
Experiment Blueprint	Constitutes the aggregated information that holistically define the services, execution environments and experiment conditions over the VITAL-5G platform and testbeds. It practically contains the previous elements such as NetApp Blueprints, Service Blueprints and testcases.	Section 8.4.1 of D1.2 [4]
Service, Testing & Experiment Manager	Responsible for the creation and execution of the experiments, including the collection and storage of the experiment results. It is activated by the vertical user, by requesting an experiment execution once the related vertical service has been successfully instantiated by the Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager.	Section 8.1.2 of D1.2 [4] Section 5.4 of D2.1 [5]
Service & Network Monitoring (and KPI collection)	A centralized monitoring platform that allows for the collection of data from the various VITAL-5G facilities during experiment execution. It monitors the progress of the experiment and of the specified KPIs, and it interacts with the Service, testing & Experiment Manager to synchronize on the data storage and processing after the experimentation cycle as finished.	Section 8.1.5 of D1.2 [4] & Section 5.3 of D2.1 [5]
Testbed monitoring tools	These are the testbed-specific monitoring tools engaged by each of the VITAL-5G facilities, to monitor the defined metrics during experiment execution and to record the specified network and infrastructure level KPIs. The recorded metrics from these tools are “sent” to the Service & Network Monitoring module via a Northbound interface.	Section 7.3.4 of D1.2 [4]
Results Analytics	The Results Analytics (RA) module receives the collected metrics from the Service & Network Monitoring module, and is responsible for the evaluation of the results after the experimentation cycle and the validation of the selected service, based on benchmarking operations, with the provided validation KPIs. This module interfaces with the VITAL-5G portal/GUI for the graphical visualization of key insights towards the experimenter, while it also produces a final experimentation report.	Section 5.5 of D2.1 [5]
Performance Diagnosis	The Performance Diagnosis (PD) module interacts with the Service & Network monitoring module, to identify under-performing elements in the experimentation chain or detecting anomalous behaviour of one of the elements, based on the collected metrics. The PD module also performs root cause analysis to identify the exact issue, in order to assist the experimenter in improving the performance of their end-to-end service.	Section 5.6 of D2.1 [5]
Portal/GUI & visualization tools	The VITAL-5G portal and Graphic User Interface (GUI) play a dual role, as it allows for the user input and experiment definition (through the creation and configuration of the various blueprints and test scripts) at the beginning of the experimentation phase (experiment design), but it is also used to provide feedback and insights to the	Section 8 of D2.1 [5]

	<p>experimenter during and after the experiment finalization. The visualization tools of the GUI are used to provide aggregated and summarized information to the experimenter based on the collected metrics and their processing from the RA and PD modules.</p>	
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It can be seen by the above descriptions of the Testing & Validation framework and procedures, that the most crucial element of the entire process is the Testcase template, as it allows the experimenter to define in detail the nature and purpose of the test, to configure all the necessary network and infrastructure elements, to define in detail the observed metrics and targeted KPIs and to specify the experiment validation conditions. Recognizing the importance of a properly defined Testcase template, the VITAL-5G partners have put significant effort in creating a template that will cover the needs of all the involved vertical stakeholders as well as potential third-party experimenters, while the same template may also be used by e.g., Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) for the definition of network oriented (vertical agnostic) testing. The VITAL-5G Testcase template and its various fields are described in the following section.

3.2 Testcase Template

A Testcase template is a document that defines all the needed information (e.g., inputs, hardware and software resources) and specifications (e.g., execution steps, testing procedure) to complete SUT experiments. It is also used to register the results of the experiments and monitor the KPIs of the whole experimental process. Table 3 shows the developed VITAL-5G Testcase template with the first fields to be for defining the Testcase ID, the trial site and the Testcase type. Section 3.2 will give a detailed description of the following fields of the VITAL-5G Testcase template:

- Description,
- Cross-referencing,
- 5G Network Environment,
- Components and Configuration,
- Key Use-case requirements and KPIs,
- Test procedure,
- Measurements,
- Expected results.

Table 3: VITAL-5G Testcase template

Testcase ID	< testcase title >	
Trial site	Site where the testcase will be executed.	
Testcase type	<UC/Service/NetApp specific vs Network Agnostic> In case of UC/Service/NetApp specific: <Reference UC/Service/NetApp ID and name>	
Description	Description of the testcase, and high-level purpose.	
Test environment and deployment	High-level graphical representation of the target environment and UC/service/NetApp deployment, identifying the placement of the various components in the testbed and highlighting the 5G network position.	
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	List of the NetApps that are relevant for this Testcase.

		When applicable, include the reference to the NetApp packages when available on the catalogue (ID, name, version, as reported in the VITAL-5G catalogue).
	Reference Service	When applicable, include the reference to the T&L Service blueprint when available on the catalogue (ID, name, version, as reported in the VITAL-5G catalogue).
	Reference Experiment	When applicable, include the reference to the Experiment blueprint when available on the catalogue (ID, name, version, as reported in the VITAL-5G catalogue).
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	Declare all necessary details regarding the network settings and configurations in order to make the testcase reproducible (e.g., number of slices, per slice subscriber characteristics (Aggregate UL/DL, RTT), per slice provisioned subscribers, number of gNBs/antennas, Frequency, MIMO settings, public or private DNN, IPv4/IPv6, etc.).
	Testcase traffic flows	Indicate all the traffic flows included in this UC, including their flow direction (DL/UL), e.g., <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On board camera to server (UL) • IoT sensor to server (UL) • Application guidance instructions to AGV (DL)
	Network performance, functional requirements & KPIs	Definition of Network performance and functional requirements and target KPIs, as driver for the network slice configuration. Where relevant, identify the target network performance for each required network slice and specify the mapping between each slice and the traffic flows defined in Testcase traffic flows subfield.
Components and Configuration	IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)	List of IoT or T&L devices required to run the experiment.
	Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)	List of network tools required to reproduce specific network conditions or collect network metrics required to execute the experiment in the target environment.
	Components of the SUT	Components which will be tested and validated from a functional and/or non-functional perspective.
	Application level Configuration	When applicable, configuration parameters of the NetApps and/or T&L service to be applied when running the experiment.
	Functional requirements	Which concrete functions of the NetApp/Service will be validated, in terms of working/not working.

Key Testcase requirements and KPIs	Service KPIs	Service KPIs – or the raw metrics to compute them - should be generated and published by NetApp/service components, e.g., number of active sessions, connected users, etc.
	Secondary Service KPIs	A secondary list of metrics/KPIs useful to interpret the values of the target service metric/KPI. Getting these measurements is not mandatory for the testcase.
Test procedure	Test location / route	Indicate the start and end point of tests. Indicate the test route (if applicable).
	Pre-conditions	Any pre-condition that needs to be met before execution of the testcase. A list of test specific pre-conditions that need to be met by the SUT including information about equipment configuration, traffic descriptor, i.e., precise description of the initial state of the SUT required to start executing the test steps.
	Testcase steps	A number of steps (actions/ procedures) that need to be performed during the execution of the test. Depending on the Testcase nature / deployment / scope, this field can also specialise the test and measurement process (methodology) of the metric for the selected underlay system.
Measurements	Methodology	The methodology to collect and evaluate the measurements, e.g., acceptable values for the monitoring time, formatting of metrics and log files, the iterations required, the monitoring frequency, etc.
	Measurement Points	Measurements Points: e.g., 5G network, application server, an end device, an AGV, a gateway, etc.
	Calculation process	If needed, any information related to the required calculation process. This information may include details related to the underlay measurements/ monitoring system. The units of the metric and, potentially, a request for first order statistics (Min, Max, etc.) can be also included.
Expected Result	Brief description of the expected results and, where necessary, their representation. These can be: specific KPI target values, specific QoS profiles for the vertical services, etc., required in the form of single values, graphs, spider diagrams, etc.	

3.2.1 Testcases Description

The first field of the template is for describing the Testcase scenario and its specific aim by giving a high-level graphical representation of the target environment and UC/service/NetApp deployment, identifying the placement of the various components in the testbed and highlighting how they are interconnected to (or through) the 5G network. Section 3.3 will give a detailed description on how this field should be completed for two different Testcases deployed in different test environment.

3.2.2 Testcase Cross-referencing

The *Cross-referencing* section of the Testcase template aims to link each Testcase with all the other relevant files, services and software components which together define each experiment in a holistic manner. Through the proper completion of these fields, the full set-up and configuration of the experiment relevant to each Testcase can be tracked and reproduced. The information in this field also provides a quick and useful overview of the key

VITAL-5G elements that are relevant for this testcase (e.g., targeted service, relevant NetApps, etc.). The *Cross-referencing* section is comprised of three distinct sub-fields, namely:

- **Relevant NetApps:** The NetApps that are relevant/engaged in this test are mentioned in this sub-field. This sub-field is only valid for the case of service-specific tests (for network tests this could be Not Applicable (N/A)). The link to a specific VITAL-5G NetApp can occur by including the ID, name and version of the relevant NetApps as reported in the VITAL-5G NetApp catalogue (see Table 4 for the list of NetApps planned by the VITAL-5G consortium partners'; additional NetApps will be introduced by third parties).
- **Reference Service:** The specific service(s) that are part of the SUT for the specific test, should be mentioned in this sub-field. As the VITAL-5G (and potentially the third-party experimenters) use case comprise multiple services, it is important to know which services are of relevance to a specific Testcase. This field is again only valid for the case of service-specific Testcases. The ID, name and version of the T&L Service blueprint can be declared in this field to offer an immediate link to the specified service.
- **Reference Experiment:** The information in this field will provide the link to the relevant experiment via the reference of the appropriate Experiment Blueprint, as mentioned on the VITAL-5G catalogue. The ID, name and version of the Experiment Blueprint should be included.

Table 4: VITAL-5G NetApps

ID	Name	Partners
VS1	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning	WINGS
VS2	Human-robot collaboration	WINGS
VS3	AI/ML based vessel/warehouse automated fault detection	NXW
VS4	Warehouse/vessel IoT environment technical visualization	NXW
VS5	Remote vessel navigation	SF/IMEC
VS6	Autonomous vessel navigation control	SF/IMEC
VS7	Navigation speed optimizer	DT
VS8	On board data collection & interfacing for vessels	BEIA/SF/IMEC
VA1a	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing	WINGS
VA1b	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing	BEIA/INCE
VA2	Remote inspection & risk assessment	WINGS/INCE
VA3	IoT Management platform	NXW
VA4	Real time digital twin	IMEC
VA5	Data stream organization	BEIA

3.2.3 Testcase 5G Network Environment

The next field called *Testcase 5G Network Environment* is focusing on the 5G network characteristics of the environment where the experiment will be conducted and it breaks down into three sub-fields:

- **5G Network settings / configuration:** The first subfield describes the 5G Network settings/configuration, in which the experimenters will declare all necessary details regarding the network settings and configurations in order to make the Testcase reproducible such as aggregate upload/download, round-trip time, per slice provisioned subscribers, number of gNBs per antenna, frequency, MIMO settings, public or private data network name, IPv4/IPv6, etc. Section 3.3 gives two Testcase examples on how to specify the 5G settings.
- **Testcase traffic flows:** This sub-field describes the Testcase traffic flows either in downlink (DL) direction or uplink (UL) direction, specifying their source and destination among the components involved in the

experiment. Examples of traffic flow include IoT sensor data stream to the server (UL direction) and application guidance instructions to AGV (DL direction).

- **Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs:** The third sub-field is for defining the network performance and network functional requirements. In the case of 5G network slicing, the experimenters must define the target network KPIs for network slice configuration and specify the mapping between each slice and the possible traffic flows in both DL and UL direction.

3.2.4 Testcase Components and Configuration

The *Testcase Components and Configuration* field is for listing the components of the SUT experiment either hardware or software and their corresponding configuration, as follows:

- **IoT/T&L components:** This sub-field is for the experimenters to list the information regarding the hardware components and their corresponding configuration during the experiment. For example, the type of sensors responsible for the IoT and T&L services and their corresponding configuration, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc.
- **Networking components:** A list of networking software tools must be completed in this sub-field such as traffic generators, network emulators and network probes, etc.
- **Components of the SUT:** The third sub-field is for describing the components of the SUT by giving a comprehensive description of their features and capabilities.
- **Application-level Configuration:** The last sub-field is dedicated to the application-level configuration such as the number of the users and device configuration settings, etc.

3.2.5 Testcase Requirements and KPIs

The fifth field will be dedicated to the *Testcase requirement and KPIs*. Usually, a Testcase is targeting a single KPI or a very small number of KPIs that have specific target values. In this field the experimenters must fill the following sub-fields:

- **Functional requirements:** The first sub-field will be for the definition of the functional requirements to validate for the different NetApps/Services in terms of working or not working.
- **Service KPIs:** The second sub-field is for completing the service KPIs that are generated by NetApp/service components such as number of active sessions, connected users, etc.
- **Secondary Service KPIs:** The third sub-field is to list the secondary service KPIs that can be useful to interpret the values of the target service metric/KPI.

3.2.6 Test Procedures

The *Test Procedure* field will provide information for the correct execution of the Testcase including a detailed procedure in order to be repeatable for future re-testing. This field will have three sub-fields, as follows:

- **Test location/route:** The first sub-field will be for indicating the start and the end points of the test including the route, if the test is related to scenarios with devices moving along a pre-defined trajectory.
- **Pre-conditions:** This sub-field will be devoted to the pre-conditions that are needed before the execution of the Testcase. This can include information about equipment configuration, traffic descriptor, and the description of the initial state of the SUT experiment.
- **Testcase steps:** The testcase actions and procedures that are needed during the different Testcase execution steps. Depending on the Testcase nature, deployment and scope, this field can also describe the test and measurement process (methodology) of the metric for the selected underlay system.

3.2.7 Measurement Procedures

The seventh field of Testcase template is *Measurements Procedures* and aims to provide the methodology of the experimental measurements and their calculation process. It contains three different sub-fields:

- **Methodology:** A detailed description of the methodology will be given in this sub-field, such as the acceptable values of the monitoring time, the number of iterations, the monitoring frequency, the formatting of metrics and log files, etc.
- **Measurement Points:** The second sub-field will describe the measurement points where monitoring probes or agents should be placed to perform the required measurements, e.g., on specific reference points at the 5G network or in particular service components or equipment, like the application server, the AGV, IoT gateways and any other device and component that was listed in the Components and Configuration field.
- **Calculation process:** The necessary information on how the calculation process should be conducted, will be provided in the final sub-field. This kind of information can include details related to the underlay measurements for Quality of Experience (QoE) and Quality of Service (QoS) of the system, such as the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) that is used as a QoE metric. Where needed, the statistics to be elaborated starting from the collected metrics can also be defined (e.g., average, standard deviation, etc.).

3.2.8 Expected Results

The last field will be the description of the *Expected Results* and their visualization through charts. The results can include specific KPI target values, specific QoS profiles for the T&L services, etc., required in the form of single values, graphs, spider diagrams, etc.

3.3 Examples of Testcase Templates

To facilitate the use of the testcase template by internal and external experimenters, two concrete examples are provided in this Section, on how to fill in a testcase, using dummy values. The first example/dummy testcase (Section 3.3.1) address a service specific test/experiment while the second example (Section 3.3.2) addresses a service agnostic (or network oriented) test/experiment.

3.3.1 Testcase for Service and/or NetApp validation

As an example, on how to complete the Testcase template for the validation of a given NetApp in a specific service, we provide Table 5, which is a dummy Testcase file for UC1 to be tested at the testbed of the port of Antwerp, Belgium. In this dummy testcase, the service specific UC1/Vessel Remote Navigation was the Testcase subject with the NetApp UC1/VS5 Remote Vessel Monitoring and all the listed values are given as an example.

Table 5: A dummy testcase of the NetApp VS5 Remote Vessel Monitoring

Testcase BE_TC#1	Dummy0_VS5_UC1
Trial site	Port of Antwerp
Testcase type	Service specific UC1 / Vessel Remote Navigation / VS5 - Remote Vessel Monitoring
Description	This test will consist in testing the video feed performance received from the vessel while navigating remotely through a narrow channel in the Port of Antwerp. The video feed is essential to monitor the vessel, since it will allow the remote captains or other users to see what is around the vessel. This way the vessel will be able to avoid objects and safely

reach its destination.

This Testcase will test in an end-to-end manner that the video generated in the on-board cameras is received in the remote monitoring dashboard of VS5 with the required quality. We will generate first testing data to accurately measure the QoS parameters and network KPIs. Secondly, we will directly use feed from the cameras and analyse the QoE perceived at the monitoring dashboard.

Test environment and deployment

Testcase Architecture

Cross-referencing

Relevant NetApps

- VS5 – Remote Vessel Navigation
- NetApp package: NAB_uc1_vs5_v01

		<p>VS7 – Navigation Speed Optimizer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc1_vs7_v01 <p>VS8 – On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc1_vs8_v01 <p>VA5 – Real-time digital twin</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc1_va5_v01
	Reference Service	<p>Vertical Service: Vessel Remote Navigation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical Service Blueprint: VSB_uc1_service2_v01
	Reference Experiment	<p>Experiment blueprint: ExpB_uc1_service2_global_tc01_v01</p>
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	<p>3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA</p> <p>5G SA RAN details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vendor: Ericsson • Software version: 1.2 • Radio Specs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Freq bands, spectrum: 2496 – 2690 Hz ○ Modulation: QPSK ○ mMIMO: 64T64R ○ Interfaces: Xn ○ RAN slice template: SST1 ○ gNB configuration: manual <p>5G SA Core</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core elements: UPF • Core Deployment: IaaS • Core deployment: manual • Core Interfaces/Exposed APIs: N4 • Slice deployment: dynamic • Slice templates: SST1 • Slice configuration: dynamic • DNN for configured slices (1/2): SNSSAI • 5G QoS: latency <p>5G Backhaul:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gNB N2/N3 integration: high speed 10Gbps • Transport network configuration: manual • Transport QoS: latency <p>5G Slices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNN: DNN1 SST1 • NS1: URLLC slice for IoT sensors (20 MHz @ 3.5GHz, TDD, QoS parameters) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 x environmental IoT sensors ○ 1x remote control module ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NS2: eMBB slices for camera feeds (100 MHz @ 3.5 GHz, TDD) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1x UHD camera ○ 2x smartphones ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency
	<p>Testcase traffic flows</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TF1: Probe testing flows to QoS measurements server (UL) on NS2 • TF2: On board camera to video feed dashboard server (UL) on NS2
	<p>Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Both flows have to perform equally from the 5G network perspective.</p> <p>For traffic flow TF1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 30 Mbps • Latency max 40 ms • Reliability min 99.980% <p>For traffic flow TF2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 30 Mbps • Latency max 40 ms • Reliability min 99.980%
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD IP Camera (Vessel) • Testing prove device, e.g., general purpose laptop with Ubuntu 18.04 (Vessel) • QoS measurements server, e.g., Ubuntu 18.04 (imec cloud) • Video feed dashboard server, e.g., Ubuntu 18.04 (imec cloud)
	<p>Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic generator using iperfv3 for DNNs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ TCP/UDP traffic load ○ Background traffic load @ 25% and 50% • Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) Round Trip Time (RTT) • Distributed Internet Traffic Generator (D-ITG) for stochastic packet generation • Network port mirroring • Core Network probes • Wireshark analysis
	<p>Components of the SUT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video feed used in VS5 generated in cameras onboarded in the vessel and received in the Monitoring Dashboard Server
	<p>Application-level Configuration</p>	<p>TF1: traffic generated with time stamps, and counters in the payload to measure one-way delay and packet loss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UDP traffic, 50Mbps, periodic, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • TCP traffic, 50Mbps, periodic, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • UDP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • TCP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UDP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size poisson [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • TCP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size poisson [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min <p>TF2: traffic generated directly with the IP camera onboarded in the vessel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • medium HD quality, H.264, RSTP • Full HD quality, H.264, RSTP • medium HD quality, mp4, WebRTC • Full HD quality, mp4, WebRTC <p>Both configurations will be tested under background traffic load at 0%, 25% and 50% in the 5G network.</p>
Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Functional requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper reception of the video feed in the Monitoring Dashboard server for e.g., detection of an obstacle in the vessel's path, or correct reception and implementation of remote navigation commands
	Service KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Max latency for testing feed (TF1) received in the QoS monitoring server < 40 ms • Min bandwidth for testing feed (TF1) received in the QoS monitoring server > 50Mbps • Min reliability for testing feed (TF1) received in the QoS monitoring server > 99.998 % • Min fps received for video feed (TF2) in the Monitoring Dashboard server > 25fps • Min Mean opinion score (MOS) perceived for video feed (TF2) in the Monitoring Dashboard server > Good (4)
	Secondary Service KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None
Test procedure	Test location / route	The test happens along the blue line in the figure, in the narrow channel between the Scheld river, and the end point B:

	<p>Pre-conditions</p>	<p>NetApps are deployed in the UC1 cloud, and have been provisioned. Vessel is equipped with at least one HD IP Cameras and it is ready to enter the channel.</p> <p>5G network has allocated the corresponding slices to the tested VS5 traffic (TF1 and TF2).</p>
	<p>Testcase steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The vessel is placed at the entrance of the channel. 2) The servers are configured to received and store the data (TF1 or TF2). 3) The vessel starts to navigate along the channel and while data is sent from the vessel. For TF1, the testing probe device will lunch the traffic generator client (iperf3 or D-ITG) with the specific configuration under testing. For TF2, the HD IP Camera will start to send the video feed with the specific configuration under testing. 4) The vessel arrives the to the dock. 5) The data is processed and KPIs are evaluated. <p>This 5-step procedure will be repeated for all configurations detailed in Application-level Configuration.</p>
<p>Measurements</p>	<p>Methodology</p>	<p>Logging format (to be started at point A):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing prove traffic TF1 is logged in CSV format upon reception. • Vessel video feed logging will be stored in video files for further QoE evaluation. <p>Logged values</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elapsed time • Instantaneous throughput (Mbps), measured at both the 5G RAN and the servers' interfaces

		<p>Number/duration of test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10-15 tests will be performed for statistical confidence and their values will be averaged. In case one of the tests presents outliers, further analysis will be carried out to check the causes. Each test should last around 1 minutes. The total duration should be around 10-15 minutes, depending on the speed of the vessel. <p>Synthetic/Background traffic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenarios with 0%, 25% and 50% background traffic at eMBB slice will be executed.
	<p>Measurement Points</p>	<p>For traffic flow TF1, measurement points at Testing probe device, UE, N3 on core UPF and N6 on server side, and on the QoS Monitoring server.</p> <p>For traffic flow TF2, measurement points at HD IP Camera, UE, N3 on core UPF, N6 on server side and on the Monitoring Dashboard server.</p> <p>From OBU to gNB: Radio Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> gNB UE1 & UE2 OBU
	<p>Calculation process</p>	<p>Values from multiple test runs will be processed to deliver the final measurements. The delivered values for all mentioned KPIs will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average Max Min 10th percentile 90th percentile <p>Throughput measurement from the 2 flows (TF1 and TF2) will be averaged to provide an average value for the eMBB channel.</p> <p>For QoE experience perceived in the Monitoring Dashboard server, the following formula will be calculated to obtain the MOS:</p> $MOS = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N R_n}{N}$ <p>Where R are the individual ratings for a given stimulus by N subjects.</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>With the conclusion of this testcase there should be a clear understanding of the performance of the video feed (and equivalent data flows e.g., testing flows for eMBB), under varying traffic conditions and configurations. The goal is to quantify the one-way</p>	

	end-to-end latency, throughput and reliability delivered by 5G at the different coverage areas where VS5 is expected to be active, with different background traffic levels on the 5G network and with different configurations that can be selected by the user of the VS5 Monitoring Dashboard server.
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3.3.2 Testcase for 5G Network Performance assessment

This subsection provides an example of a network oriented (or service agnostic) Testcase for conducting 5G network performance assessment experiments, see Table 6.

Table 6: A dummy Testcase report for conducting 5G network performance assessment

Testcase ID	Dummy1_Galati_5Gtest1		
Trial site	Galati trial site		
Testcase type	5G Network Performance		
Description	<p>The purpose of this test is to measure 5G network KPIs and validate its performance according to the use case requirements that are identified for each use case, including the NetApps service instantiation, network slice deployment, resource orchestration and available resources from testbeds pool (RAM, CPU, Network).</p> <p>The network test consists of measuring and validating the network required KPIs in term of latency, throughput and network availability and reliability for 5G facilities. Infrastructure KPIs measurements will start from the end device site and end at packet core site. KPIs measurements will be performed for each type of service (service slice aware).</p>		
Test environment and deployment	<p style="text-align: center;">Testcase measurement architecture</p>		
Cross-referencing	<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%;">Relevant</td> <td>N/A (These values are just for testcases related to NetApps or vertical</td> </tr> </table>	Relevant	N/A (These values are just for testcases related to NetApps or vertical
Relevant	N/A (These values are just for testcases related to NetApps or vertical		

	NetApps	services.)
	Reference Service	N/A
	Reference Experiment	N/A
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	<p>3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA</p> <p>5G SA RAN details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vendor: Ericsson • Software version: 1.2 • Radio Specs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Freq bands, spectrum: 2496 – 2690 Hz ○ Modulation: QPSK ○ mMIMO: 64T64R ○ Interfaces: Xn ○ RAN slice template: SST1 ○ gNB configuration: manual <p>5G SA Core:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core elements: UPF • Core Deployment: IaaS • Core deployment: manual • Core Interfaces/Exposed APIs: N4 • Slice deployment: dynamic • Slice templates: SST1 • Slice configuration: dynamic • DNN for configured slices (1/2): SNSSAI • 5G QoS: latency <p>5G Backhaul:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gNB N2/N3 integration: high speed 10Gbps • Transport network configuration: manual • Transport QoS: latency <p>5G Slices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNN: DNN1 SST1 • NS1: URLLC slice for IoT sensors (20 MHz @ 3.5GHz, TDD, QoS parameters) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency <p>Facility Architecture for KPIs/performance:</p>

	<p>Testcase traffic flows</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic flow 1 from Probe 1 through the specific network slice to probes 2,3,4 (UL measurement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • Traffic flow 2 from Probe 2,3,4 through the specific network slice to probe 1 (DL measurement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • Traffic flow 3 for Latency measurements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX 																
	<p>Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Based on D1.1 network requirements, the measured KPIs should have the values that are presented in the following table for the end-to-end measurement.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="753 978 1318 1318"> <thead> <tr> <th>KPI</th> <th>Port of Antwerp</th> <th>Galati Port</th> <th>Athens logistics hub</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Latency (max)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Throughput (min)</td> <td>30</td> <td>20</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Availability (min)</td> <td>99,99%</td> <td>99,99%</td> <td>99,999%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>KPIs measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency between user service end-points • User data (UL/DL) • Packet loss, jitter • Reliability (MIN/MAX): 99,99%-99,9999% • Availability (MIN/MAX): 99,99%-99,9999% • Area traffic density • E2E Service slice instantiation 	KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub	Latency (max)	20	20	20	Throughput (min)	30	20	30	Availability (min)	99,99%	99,99%	99,999%
KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub															
Latency (max)	20	20	20															
Throughput (min)	30	20	30															
Availability (min)	99,99%	99,99%	99,999%															
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<p>N/A</p>																
	<p>Networking components</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic generator using iperfv3 																

	(e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICMP tool • Core Network probes • Monitoring software tools • Platform for KPIs analysis and results
	Components of the SUT	N/A
	Application-level Configuration	N/A
Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Functional requirements	N/A
	Service KPIs	N/A (network KPIs will be measured)
	Secondary Service KPIs	N/A
Test procedure	Test location / route	The test start point will be the end device and the end point will be set after packet core. The distance of the start and the end points varies depending on the trial site.
	Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G network integration has to be completed. • Probes have to be installed on proper spots. • 5G service slice has been instantiated. • Probes and monitoring software tools installed.
	Testcase steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Probe installed • Traffic is generated through the selected network slice (use of ICMP/ping and iPerf) • Probes and monitoring tools receive the traffic • Result analysis is performed • KPIs are measured and evaluated, KPIs tables are completed • Final results analysis
Measurements	Methodology	<p>Latency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To estimate the latency, packets will be transferred through the network (from probe 1 to probes 2,3 and 4) and the time that a packet needs to be received from probes 2, 3 and 4 will be measured <p>Throughput</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To estimate the UL throughput, packets will be transferred through the network (from probe 1 to probes 2,3 and 4). Packets sent will be measure, as well as packets received. • To estimate the DL throughput, packets will be transferred through the network (from probes 2,3 and 4 to probe 1).

		<p>Packets sent will be measure, as well as packets received.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure of actual packet delivery. <p>Availability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To estimate the service availability packet error rate during the operation of a service will be measured. • Measure the packet error rate at the IP/Application layer. <p>Reliability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the network service reliability during a preset estimation interval. • 5G Network functionality: Reliability is the success probability of packet transmission within a required maximum time • Measure the packet error rate at the IP/Application layer.
	<p>Measurement Points</p>	<p>Network probes and software collection tools will be used and installed in different network part, as per facilities availability, to collect the network measurements, for example:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Radio to BBU: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. probe 1 will be installed in the end device site and probe 2 will be installed in BBU 2) Radio to the end of POTP <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. probe 1 will be installed in the end device site and probe 3 will be installed before packet core 3) Radio to the end of packet core <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. probe 1 will be installed in the end device site and probe 4 will be installed after packet core 4) Network infrastructure probes for IaaS/CaaS (infrastructure load) for NetApps VNFs/VMs and CNFs
	<p>Calculation process</p>	<p>Values to be measured and computed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency (Average) in ms • Latency (Max) in ms • Latency (Min) in ms • Availability min in % • Throughput (Average) in Mbps • Throughput (Max) in Mbps • Throughput (Min) in Mbps
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>The network test expects to provide network KPIs measurements. These measurements include metrics related to the service that is provided to end users. Therefore, the expected results should validate the optimal performance of the network according to the network requirements that have been identified for each use case and are presented in the following table.</p>	

		KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub
		Latency (max)	20	20	20
		Throughput (min)	30	20	30
		Availability (min)	99.99%	99.99%	99,999%

4 Business Validation in VITAL-5G

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the methodology that will be followed to gather business-related feedback from users involved in the trials. The approach taken will target users from within the project in addition to those external actors invited to use VITAL-5G assets as part of the activities targeting third party experimenters.

The overall approach is guided by the Lean Startup methodology, which is described in the next section.

4.1 Lean Startup Methodology

Lean Startup (LS) is the prevalent business experimentation methodology to generate and test business models, and it became popular from a series of management books [6], [7]. The basic principle behind the LS methodology is based on hypothesis testing by “getting out of the building” to evaluate ideas with real customers.

The whole LS methodology process centres around an iterative process with three steps: Build, Measure, and Learn. The build step is about the creation of a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) that will be used to test and verify the business model hypotheses. A representative sample of the various customer segments will be approached to use the MVP and provide feedback. The second step is to assess the feedback from customers on the use of the MVP, in order to extract the information needed to fine-tune both the product and the value proposition. The feedback is usually questionnaires that cover critical information about all the aspects of the customer needs and how well the MVP was able to satisfy those needs. The final step of the LS methodology is to learn from the feedback and either try to fix the aspects that are wrong with the product/business model to better meet customer needs, or stop the whole endeavour, to avoid wasting resources.

4.2 Overview of Business Validation Approach

In this aspect of the project the general approach of the Lean Startup methodology, discussed in Section 4.1, will be followed. The overall goal is to explore if the trials being run as part of VITAL-5G meet the business-related needs of the use case T&L vertical partners. The approach therefore needs to investigate to what extent the trials solve business-related problems, and what aspects of the implementation of the use case and functionality offered by the trials are suitable for market deployment. Critical to this feedback is requesting views on how to improve the offering, so an understanding of the required improvements can be developed and improvements made to the assets produced in the project.

The following sub-sections cover different user types from whom feedback will be requested. Depending on the role within the use case trials, different information will be requested from these actors. The goal of this approach is to provide more targeted user feedback for helping to improve the VITAL-5G assets. The questions derived from an analysis of these user groups is then provided in Section 4.3.

4.2.1 Use Case Business-Related Feedback

In the design of the use cases, the business goals of certain partners were identified to help establish the targets of each use case. These goals are highlighted in Tables 3, 6, and 9 of D1.1, and mainly relate to the business targets of the T&L vertical partners (SF, NAV, ATG, DIA). In many ways these are the “customers” of the use cases and it is therefore essential to gather their feedback to determine if the services being deployed in the use case pilots are commercially relevant to them. Gathering as much detail as possible is important to get the “Use Case Customer” feedback on where the trials fail to meet expectations and why that is the case. This information can then be used to determine what updates are needed to improve the services/solutions being offered by the project.

Feedback will also be solicited from the key commercial partners of VITAL-5G who will be supplying the T&L services as part of the use cases. This is important as it helps build an understanding from key users involved in

the use case of the extent to which the services/solutions produced during the project and tested during the trials, represent viable commercial assets for the partners involved. Such “Use Case Suppliers” would be represented by BEIA and WINGS, and feedback will be targeted at determining if the solutions produced during the project could be sold by these companies and, if not, what improvements would need to be made to make them more mature/commercially-relevant for these SMEs. The goal is therefore to help assess how much “commercial-promise” offering the T&L services being implemented in the trials would have for the SMEs involved. These potential commercial offerings are distinct from the VITAL-5G experimentation platform, which is seen as a separate commercial asset, used to develop and test the services and components being produced in the project. The feedback on the platform and its features, etc. will be discussed in the next sub-section.

4.2.2 Platform User Feedback

The VITAL-5G experimentation platform has been identified as a potential commercial asset arising from the project and will be investigated further in the development of the commercialisation strategy in WP5. For this reason, feedback from the platform users and the network operators is also important to help assess the commercial-viability of the platform and of the experimentation services, respectively. This will involve targeting the users of the platform involved in setting up and running experiments, developing and testing NetApps and/or network components, those using the dashboards, etc. Feedback will be sought on features available, usability, documentation, and needs related to training/support.

Depending on how actors are accessing the platform and their skillset, distinctly different feedback is expected. For example, the answers for those developing VNF or network orchestration NetApps should be different to those using the NetApps made available by the VITAL-5G partners to help rapidly deploy new T&L services. For this reason, questions for this user group should be kept broad in order to allow questions to be meaningful for the full range of users expected to engage with the VITAL-5G platform.

It is noted that some of the consortium partners in the Platform User group will also be part of the UC Supplier group (discussed above). These partners will be requested to provide feedback for both the T&L services developed as part of the UCs, as well as the experimentation platform. This is to ensure the platform is assessed as a separate asset and direct feedback on the platform’s use in developing NetApps, experimenting with services, etc. is captured.

The partners developing various components of the experimentation platform (e.g., NXW, EBOS, ...), will be included in this group, to ensure their assessment of the commercial-readiness of the platform is also captured.

4.2.3 Third-Party Experimenter Feedback

A core aspect of the VITAL-5G project is to offer third-parties the ability to experiment using the assets produced during VITAL-5G. Such activities represent an opportunity to test the project’s assets with a wider group of users beyond the consortium members. Following their experiments, these third-parties will also be targeted for gathering feedback on aspects of VITAL-5G that are seen as important/commercially-relevant, and on those aspects that need further improvement.

As the interests of the third-parties are likely to be broad and will vary in terms of which VITAL-5G assets they will experiment with, the questions that will be asked will need to be customised for the different types of users. Direction will, in general, be taken from the feedback received from the various consortium partners, in particular from the “Platform Users” group (as discussed above), as this is the type of user group third parties are most likely to be part of. The exact questionnaire definition to be used for third party experimenters will be developed by Task 6.3, based on the target groups to be defined for third party experimentation per facility, as well as for the platform itself, in collaboration with WP5. More detailed results on the experimenter targets groups, the associated business plan depending on the targeted service and the engagement process with third parties (invitation, proposal submission and evaluation, feedback and questionnaires) will be reported in the upcoming deliverables D5.2 and D6.3, both due for M18.

4.3 Business Validation Questionnaires

The questionnaires presented in this section have resulted from an analysis of the user types discussed in the preceding sub-section. Questions have been kept as open as possible to give respondents the freedom to address the questions in the manner they deem most appropriate, based on their experience of using the project assets.

The questions selected are indicative and can be refined as the technical work develops, especially in cases where project partners determine that more specific information is needed from specific user groups.

The questions described below will also be transferred to an online tool (such as Google Forms, or similar) to facilitate gathering the feedback.

4.3.1 Use Case Customer Questions

1. Identification information – organisation, role
2. Based on your interaction with the VITAL-5G trials:
 - a. To what extent does the VITAL-5G solution help you achieve your business goals?
 - i. Scale (1-10)
 - ii. Please elaborate on your response.
 - b. What would you say are the features of most benefit to your organisation? Would you see these being used on a day-to-day basis?
 - c. What aspects of the trials would you like to see improved?
 - d. Are there additional features that you would suggest adding? Are these features essential or nice-to-haves, and why are these features needed?
 - e. What was the biggest roadblock for you when using the VITAL-5G solutions during the trials?
3. If the VITAL-5G solution was refined and provided as a commercially-available service, how likely would you be to pay for this service?
 - a. Scale 1-10
4. Do you have any additional comments or feedback?

4.3.2 Use Case Supplier Questions

1. Identification information – organisation, role
2. Based on your experience with the VITAL-5G trials:
 - a. On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rank the success of the trial?
 - i. Please elaborate
 - b. What aspects of the trials worked well?
 - i. Please elaborate on the reasoning behind your choices.
 - c. What aspects of the trials would you like to see improved and how could they be improved?
 - d. What was the biggest roadblock for you when using the VITAL-5G solutions during the trials?
 - e. Are there additional features that you would suggest adding to improve the trial solution? Are these features essential or nice-to-haves, and why are these features needed?
 - f. How far is the finalised trial solution from a real product?
 - i. Please provide a frank assessment of what is needed to make the VITAL-5G assets viable solutions in your company's portfolio.
 - g. On a scale of 1 to 10, to what extent does the VITAL-5G solution help you achieve your business goals?
 - i. Please elaborate on your response.
3. Do you have any additional comments or feedback?

4.3.3 Platform User Questions

1. Identification information – organisation, role
2. Based on your experience with the VITAL-5G platform:
 - a. On a scale of 1 to 10, how well did the VITAL-5G platform meet your needs?
 - i. Please elaborate
 - b. What features of the platform worked well?
 - i. Please elaborate on the reasoning behind your choices.
 - c. What features of the platform would you like to see improved and how could they be improved?
 - d. What was the biggest roadblock for you when using the VITAL-5G platform during the trials?
 - e. Are there additional features that you would suggest adding to improve the VITAL-5G platform? Are these features essential or nice-to-haves, and why are these features needed?
 - f. On a scale of 1 to 10, to what extent does the VITAL-5G solution help you achieve your business goals?
 - i. Please elaborate on your response.
 - g. [For platform developers] How far is the finalised trial solution from a real product?
 - i. Please provide a frank assessment of what is needed to make the VITAL-5G assets viable solutions in your company's portfolio.
3. Do you have any additional comments or feedback?

5 Third-Party Engagement

The purpose of this section is to outline the strategy that will be implemented by VITAL-5G to engage third-party experimenters. The reader is referred to Section 3.4 of deliverable D1.2 [4] for a more detailed description of the particular technology assets third parties will have access to at each of the VITAL-5G test sites.

Third party engagement is critical to VITAL-5G to ensure the experimentation facilities and associated software assets are available to third party actors, who would not otherwise have access to such flexible infrastructure and 5G connectivity for experimentally evaluate pre-commercial versions of their 5G-enabled applications and services. The engagement with third parties is also essential to guide the development of assets within the project, as third parties experimenting on the VITAL-5G platform and with the project's facilities will be able to provide important feedback to the project based on their experience. Such feedback is essential for ensuring the opinions and experiences of external parties are added to those of the consortium members, which provides a more varied view of the project assets and a better understanding of how well the VITAL-5G assets address real market needs. Such feedback will be essential in the later stages of the project, particularly for deliverable D1.3 (due M26), which aims to provide a final version of the platform and repository specifications taking into account experimenters' feedback.

The project aims to facilitate third-party experimenters accessing the VITAL-5G platform, equipment, services, and NetApps to help broaden the potential impact of the project's assets. Of particular interest is ensuring the software assets and infrastructure is made available to external vertical players, particularly innovative SMEs looking to develop 5G-enabled services for commercial deployment. In this way, the VITAL-5G assets have the potential to help such organisations understand the benefits of deploying T&L services on 5G networks, which could potentially lead to the creation of updated business models. It is noted that although the project focuses on T&L stakeholders (researchers, SMEs, port agencies, port authorities, etc.), third party experimentation will be open to any vertical application developer requiring 5G connectivity and wishing to understand the implementation challenges of deploying their applications on 5G networks.

VITAL-5G is targeting two distinct categories of third-party experimenters, namely "Vertical Experimenters" and "NetApp Developers", as defined in Section 3.4 of deliverable D1.2. Vertical Experimenters are seen as users of the existing NetApps, services and equipment created by the VITAL-5G partners, who will experiment with these assets to better understand the technical and business benefits of deploying 5G services. The NetApp Developers group is seen as those possessing the technical skills to create the building blocks for their own services or for third party services, which can be deployed and validated within the VITAL-5G trial facilities. The feedback from the latter would help to explore the business ecosystem and commercial needs of actors active in NetApp development. Such market-relevant insight will be essential to develop a stronger understanding of the commercial needs of the NetApp developers.

Within VITAL-5G there are two tasks dedicated to supporting the interaction with third parties: Task 6.3 (Capacity building programme, led by IMEC) and Task 4.3 (External third party experimentation and validation, led by BEIA):

- The objectives of the Capacity Building Programme in Task 6.3 are to promote the capabilities of the 5G experimentation facilities, upon which third parties can potentially test and validate their applications. Task 6.3 is the key task within the project that assists with discovering, training and more generally interacting with the third-party experimenters. An overview of the steps that will be taken to engage third parties as part of this task is given in Section 5.2.
- Task 4.3 has dedicated resources to facilitate third parties experimenting with VITAL-5G assets and will closely cooperate with Task 6.3, facilitating the training and technical support that is essential for successful engagement of third-party experimenters. Task 4.3 is therefore responsible for supporting experimenters during NetApp onboarding, experiment setup, execution and results collection.

The details in the following sub-sections represent the initial plans on third party engagement and will be developed further in the next phase of the project, particularly as Task 6.3 (Capacity building programme)

develops. The specific phases of the engagement process where Tasks 4.3 and 6.3 contribute are highlighted in Table 4 in the next sub-section.

5.1 Overview of the Engagement Process

The purpose of the third-party engagement process is to provide the framework for experimenters to access VITAL-5G assets in order to broaden the scope of those impacted by the project beyond the project’s consortium members. The high-level outline of this process is to execute the necessary steps to create awareness of the experimentation services and capabilities offered by VITAL-5G, with messaging particularly focused on SMEs, and to enable expressions of interest to be prepared, submitted and evaluated. The process will then outline how, following selection of appropriate proposals, more detailed engagement with the VITAL-5G partners will occur, in order to plan the specifics of the proposed experiments and how assistance will be provided during their execution. As mentioned in the previous section, soliciting feedback from the third-party experimenters will be essential to help refine the VITAL-5G assets and assess the success of the engagement process.

In order to develop the overview of this engagement process, as presented in Table 7, reference was made to the 5GINFIRE project (particularly their deliverable D7.1 [8]), where a similar third-party engagement process was outlined. Table 7 is the initial overview of the process and will be refined as the project matures.

Table 7: Overview of the third-party engagement process

Step Number	Step Name	Description	Contributing Task(s)
1.	Develop invitation details and supporting material	<p>Create text to describe the open invitation to be used in communications with potential third-party experimenters, which advertises the opportunity to test with the VITAL-5G assets. This will provide an analytical description of the assets available to third parties (currently summarized in D1.2 [4]) and provide links to descriptions of example use cases, relevant project results, and publications that will help third parties propose suitable / feasible experiments. The invitation will include details of planned workshops / hackathons, where further details can be provided to prospective third-party experimenters. This material will be created and/or collated by the partners active in Task 6.3 and is discussed in more detail in Section 5.2.</p> <p>As part of this invitation, eligibility criteria will be provided, along with an overview of the selection criteria. These will be defined in the next phase of work in Task 6.3, and will likely follow the guidance provided by 5GINFIRE D7.1 [8]. A link to the proposal form and associated submission instructions will also be provided.</p>	T6.3
2.	Promote invitation	Use the invitation details from Step 1 as part of communication activities and networking events (such as workshops and hackathons) to promote the call for expressions of interest. Such activities will occur as part of Task 6.3, an overview of which is provided in Section 5.2.	T6.3
3.	Proposal phase	Templates will be made available to streamline the submission of ideas and to streamline the later proposal review phase of the engagement process. A dedicated email address has been created to receive proposals and support questions. The address is	T6.3

		experimenters@vital-5g.com and has been set up by EBOS. A nominated partner active in T6.3 will monitor this mailbox and direct any support questions to appropriate consortium members.	
4.	Evaluation phase	<p>This phase will evaluate and rank each proposal submitted according to eligibility and selection criteria. An evaluation committee will be convened from VITAL-5G consortium members and evaluation forms will be created to record the outcome of the evaluation for each proposal. The evaluation committee will comprise relevant technical experts from the testbed side and from the VITAL-5G platform side, who are selected based on the particulars of the proposed experiment, i.e., depending on the trial facility that the third-party experimenter(s) would like to use, the corresponding partners from that facility will have a leading role in the evaluation committee.</p> <p>The number and type of experiments to be selected for further engagement will depend on the details of the proposed experiments and the resources available to support these tests. Decisions on the number of proposed experiments to go ahead with will be made by the use case teams supporting the third-party experimenters as part of Task 4.3.</p>	T6.3, T4.3
5.	Detailed engagement phase	This phase will cover the activities occurring after third-party experiments have been approved. The initial step of this phase will be to conduct a kick-off meeting between the third parties and the supporting VITAL-5G consortium members. Following this the third parties will engage in detailed experiment planning using the internal planning tools available from Task 4.1. It is expected that this phase will involve numerous discussions with VITAL-5G facility / testbed representatives, in order to effectively plan the experiments, and will include focused training sessions on the use of VITAL-5G assets relevant to the proposed experiment. Critical to this will be to define a precise schedule and deadlines for planning and experimentation to be completed. This is to ensure such activities are conducted in a timely fashion that aligns with the project's timelines.	T6.3, T4.3
6.	Experiment execution phase	Execution of the planned experiments and recording of appropriate metrics. In this phase, VITAL-5G technicians will support the experimentation activities, assisting in the usage of the VITAL-5G platform and, if needed, helping with configurations or installations that may be required at the testbed level.	T4.3
7.	Feedback phase	The specifics of the feedback to be requested from third parties will depend on the type of experiment conducted and the type of user role the third-party experimenter assumes while conducting experiments (as discussed in Section 4.2).	T6.3

		One key item of feedback will be to report on the experiment results and the experiences of executing the experiments using the VITAL-5G assets.	
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5.2 Engagement Activities

As introduced previously, the third-party experiments will be either “vertical experimenters” or “NetApp developers”. Vertical experimenters are mainly expected to be SMEs or even public entities, such as port authorities or local public administrations. On the other hand, while NetApp developers will be mostly SMEs, there may be a number of industry/academic research groups wanting to test their own technologies in the VITAL-5G testbeds by deploying them as NetApps.

In order to engage such third-party experiments, we foresee three main activity streams to effectively promote the outcomes of the project:

- **Engagement Events:** we will participate in conferences and workshops co-located with major events (e.g., 5G Summit) as mean to engage new players in VITAL-5G and showing real demos. Also, we plan to organized several hackathons (at least one per UC site) to allow third-party experimenters to test the potential of VITAL-5G and get to know the VITAL-5G ecosystem. Additionally, for the selected third-party experimenters, we will organize more technical sessions such as webinars, training workshops and periodic Q&A sessions.
- **Scientific Conferences:** these events will serve as a forum where the third-party experimenters can show their results, attracting new experimenters, and strengthening the community through the interaction between experimenters themselves, researchers and facility providers. Some examples of target conferences are EuCNC (European Conference on Networks and Communications), TNC (TERENA Networking Conference), CNERT (Workshop on Computer and Networking Experimental Research using Testbeds), etc.
- **Summer Schools:** depending on the third-party experimenters’ profiles (e.g., in case third-party experimenters include many PhD students or academic researchers), we will evaluate the possibility of hosting summer schools, where students, researchers or SMEs can receive training to access the VITAL-5G platform and tutorials on how design and run experiments in a series of sessions programmed during several days. This would be done in coordinated manner with the engagement events described above.

The timings will be planned according the VITAL-5G platform development roadmap and the estimated releases of its components. In this sense, since the first full version of the platform is planned by M23, the engagement activities will commence from the second year of the project in order to have reach the first external users by M23.

Before this period, the effort will be put in disseminating the project in relevant venues (engineering conferences and workshops). During the M23-M29 period most of the events related with actual engaging of new third-party experimenters will be scheduled, such as real demos in engineering conferences and workshops, webinars and hackathons. Finally, during M30-36, additional technical training workshops for specific components and periodic Q&A sessions will be planned ensure a smooth interaction between engaged third-party experimenters and the VITAL-5G platform. As commented before, a more detailed plan of such activities will be provided in M18 in D6.3.

5.3 Third Party Engagement KPIs

This section intends to briefly outline the KPIs that will be tracked in order to quantify the level of engagement of third parties with VITAL-5G. Where possible, the data used to measure these KPIs will be requested as part of monitoring workshop/hackathon participation and in the proposal application form. The list in Table 8 is the initial set of KPIs to be monitored and this will be revised in the next phase of the work in Task 6.3.

Table 8: Third Party Engagement KPIs

KPI ID	KPI Description
TPE_1	Number of experiment proposals received
TPE_2	Number of experiments executed by third parties
TPE_3	Number of experiments selected for “Detailed engagement phase”, as described in Table 7
TPE_4	Number of new NetApps submitted to the VITAL-5G repository
TPE_5	Number of public NetApps from VITAL-5G repository re-used by third-party experimenters
TPE_6	Number, type and duration of interventions required by VITAL-5G technicians in support of third-party experiments, possibly with details about the profile of the VITAL-5G technicians
TPE_7	Average and maximum amount of computing resources used in each testbed for third-party experiments and related duration
TPE_8	Number and characteristics of 5G network slices, per testbed, created for third party experiments
TPE_9	Number of third-party experiments interacting with internal IoT/T&L assets of the testbeds, quantity and type of these assets
TPE_10	Number of workshops/hackathons organised by Task 6.3 and number of registered users at these events
TPE_11	Number of third-party user accounts activated on VITAL-5G platform
TPE_12	Number of third parties engaging with VITAL-5G from different organisation types (e.g., SMEs, Academia, Research Institutions, etc.)
TPE_13	Number of third parties engaging with VITAL-5G from different countries

6 Conclusions

This deliverable has described the testing and validation methodology of the VITAL-5G platform for both technology and business aspects. For the former, we had provided a detailed description of the framework to be used in order to enable the testing and validation of the NetApp-based T&L services over the VITAL-5G platform. Section 3.1 has given a comprehensive description of testing and validation procedure that concludes in Section 3.2 with the presentation of the Testcase template and the two dummy Testcase reports. That will be used as examples by the experimenters and the facility providers to document and present the KPIs of their work. These results will be used extensively in WP4 *“Testing and Validation Vertical Trials”* for the completion of the different vertical scenarios, VITAL-5G NetApp validation and the third-party experiments. Additionally, the developed tools and framework will be applied in WP3 *“5G Testbed and Infrastructure Upgrades & Integration”* to implement and document all the necessary upgrades and extensions onto the 5G-testbeds and vertical infrastructures.

As for the business aspects of the project, Section 4 has described the process to gather business-related feedback from users involved in the trials. A set of questionnaires, surveys and focused group workshops directly engaging external stakeholders and third-party experimenters is given. Furthermore, Section 5 has given the initial version of the third-party engagement process with engagement activities and KPIs. This is quite important for completing the TaaS business model of the VITAL-5G platform and to ensure market relevance. All business validation results together with the third-party engagement roadmap will be used in all the tasks of WP5 *“Commercialization and Innovation”*, in T4.3 *“External third party experimentation and validation”* and in T6.3 *“Capacity building programme”*.

7 References

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